

Scope: Technology Management

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14873930

VLEARNY Journal of Business
2 (1) 2025, 33-41, <https://vlearn.com/journal/>
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Submitted: 10 Sep, 2024
Revised: 2 Nov, 2024
Accepted: 17 Dec, 2024
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ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS IN CYBERSECURITY: A HOLISTIC OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIONS AND APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Cybersecurity is an essential field focused on protecting systems, networks, and data from digital threats. With the rapid growth of the Internet and the rise in cyberattacks, particularly on Internet of Things (IoT) networks, developing advanced tools is crucial. This paper provides an overview of deep learning (DL) techniques applied in cybersecurity, including methods like deep belief networks, generative adversarial networks, and recurrent neural networks, comparing them to traditional shallow learning approaches. It also highlights the growing cyberattacks in IoT networks and the effectiveness of DL methods in mitigating these threats. Studies discussed include DL applications in malware detection, classification, intrusion detection, and cyberattacks like spam and network traffic. For instance, restricted Boltzmann machines achieved 99.72% accuracy, while LSTM reached 99.80% on the KDD Cup 99 dataset. The paper concludes by emphasizing the role of cybersecurity in ensuring the reliability of IoT-driven healthcare systems and improving security outcomes.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Deep Learning, Internet of Things (IoT), Malware Detection, Intrusion Detection.

Citation of this paper: Anil, A., Patel, C. Y. M., Shrikant, B. K., & B.S, C. (2025). Artificial neural networks in cybersecurity: A holistic overview of innovations and applications. VLEARNY Journal of Business, 2(1), 33-41. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14873930>

I. INTRODUCTION:

Cybersecurity, or information technology security, encompasses a wide range of techniques and technologies designed to protect networks, software, and data from attacks. Cyber defense mechanisms operate at various levels, including the network, data, host, and application levels.

Essential cybersecurity tools, such as firewalls and intrusion detection and prevention systems, are constantly active to identify security breaches and thwart attacks. The emergence of Internet of Things (IoT) networks has intensified the demand for robust cybersecurity measures. IoT networks are particularly vulnerable to various security

threats, with some attacks being easily recognizable and manageable. However, attackers often develop zero-day exploits, which emerge as soon as a vulnerability is identified, posing significant risks since they lack prior history. Additionally, organizations must protect against insider threats, where authorized personnel misuse access to sensitive systems. This task is complicated by the vast amounts of data generated by numerous cyber-enabled devices. Data Science plays a crucial role in analyzing this data, particularly from security information and event management (SIEM) systems, which can overwhelm security experts with alerts about patterns and anomalies. While previous reviews have highlighted machine learning (ML) applications for cybersecurity, they have not adequately addressed deep learning methods. This paper aims to fill that gap by reviewing the application of DL in cybersecurity, discussing the differences between DL and shallow learning, and reporting on the results of various DL methods.

II. Deep Learning and Machine Learning

Both Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) are branches of artificial intelligence (AI), but they differ in several key aspects:

- a) **Data Dependency:** DL models require large datasets to perform optimally, as they need substantial data to accurately capture patterns. In contrast, ML algorithms can work effectively with smaller datasets, as they often follow predefined rules to learn from the data.
- b) **Hardware Requirements:** Training DL models typically demands specialized hardware like Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), which are essential for handling the numerous matrix operations involved. On the other hand, most ML

algorithms can run on standard hardware without needing high-performance computing resources like GPUs.

- c) **Feature Extraction:** Feature processing, the step of reducing data complexity through domain-specific knowledge, plays a crucial role in both ML and DL. In traditional ML, this process requires manual feature extraction based on domain expertise, which can be time-consuming and requires specialized knowledge.
- d) **Execution Time:** The training phase for DL models is often time-consuming, due to their complex architectures and large number of parameters, sometimes taking days to complete. However, DL models compensate with faster testing times. Conversely, ML models typically require much less time to train, often completing in seconds or hours, but may take longer during the testing phase compared to DL models. On the other hand, ML models are more efficient for smaller datasets and lower hardware demands but require manual feature engineering and have longer testing times.

III. DL APPROACHES IN CYBER SECURITY

This section illustrates different types of DL methods used in cyber security.

A. Deep Belief Networks:

Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) were introduced by Geoffrey Hinton in a seminal paper and represent a specific type of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). DBNs consist of multiple layers of hidden variables, where each layer is connected to the adjacent one, but there are no connections between units within the same layer. The primary purpose of DBNs is to efficiently learn feature representations from large datasets. Figure 1 depicts different types of DBN architectures.

Figure 1: Deep belief Networks

B. Autoencoder:

An autoencoder is an unsupervised learning method where the input is provided as a vector, and the network's goal is to reproduce the input at the output layer. By modifying the dimensionality of the recreated input, the autoencoder can generate either lower or higher- dimensional representations of the original data. A denoising autoencoder is useful for removing noise from the data, allowing the network to reconstruct the original input from a corrupted version. Figure 2 demonstrates a simple autoencoder structure.

C. Recurrent Neural Network:

A recurrent neural network (RNN) is a type of neural network where the nodes are connected in a directed graph, as illustrated in Figure 3. This architecture allows the network to maintain an internal state, enabling it to model dynamic, sequential data. RNNs are capable of processing sequences of inputs by using their internal memory, with signals traveling both forward and backward through the network via loops. This ability to handle arbitrary input sequences makes RNNs particularly effective for tasks involving temporal data [13-15] .

Training recurrent neural networks (RNNs) is typically challenging due to the vanishing gradient problem. One such improvement is the long short-term memory (LSTM) network, introduced by Hochreiter and Schmid Huber in 1997 . LSTM has significantly impacted speech recognition and has outperformed traditional models in several speech-related tasks.

Figure 3: RNN

D. Convolutional Neural Network:

A convolutional neural network (CNN) is a type of deep neural network specifically designed to process and analyze visual data. When an image, whether colored or grayscale, is input into the network, it is represented as a 2D array of pixels. CNNs are not limited to visual data and are also used for handling audio spectrograms, which are similarly represented as 2D arrays. The architecture of a CNN consists of three main types of layers: convolution layers, pooling layers, and classification layers. These layers work together to extract features and perform tasks such as image recognition. Figure 4 provides a visual representation of a CNN.

Figure 4: Convolutional Neural Network

E. Generative Adversarial Networks:

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are a type of unsupervised machine learning where two neural networks compete against each other in a zero-sum game. The concept was introduced by Goodfellow. As illustrated in Figure 5, GANs consist of two main components: a generator and a discriminator. The generator creates output data with features resembling real- world data, while the discriminator evaluates whether the input data is real or generated. GANs have a wide

range of applications, including optical flow estimation, caption generation, image enhancement, and Deep Convolutional GANs (DCGANs) used by Facebook.

Figure 5. Generative Adversarial Networks

F. Recursive Neural Network:

Recursive neural networks utilize a set of weights that are applied recursively to multiple inputs. Initially, the first two inputs are combined and fed into the model as a single entity. The output from one node is subsequently used as an input for the next node in the sequence. This type of architecture is commonly employed in natural language processing tasks and image segmentation applications.

Recursive Neural Net

Figure 6: Recursive Neural Networks

IV. COMPARISON BETWEEN SHALLOW LEARNING AND DL

DL has various layers, as depicted in figure 6. Also, in DL, it is a network of deep layers of hidden layers, whereas in shallow neural networks, there are typically 1-hidden layer. However, there are two types of shallow network architecture: supervised and unsupervised. In supervised learning, the labels are known while learning a work. The DL Architecture is of three types: unsupervised, hybrid and Supervised. Advance feature extraction in shallow neural networks is done separately as they consist of only one hidden layer. However, deep networks can learn with much more computational power, several GPUs are required for DL methods and it takes too much time to train DL models [19].

Figure 7. Deep Neural Network

Cyber Attack	DL Method	Dataset	Research Paper
Malware	Detection and Classification		

CNN	Microsoft Malware Classification Challenge [108]	[41]
Autoencoder	Comodo Cloud Security Center [119]	[33]
Autoencoder	Dataset of call sequence in Public malware API [130]	[42]
CNN	Genome Project [120], McAfee Labs	[32]
CNN RNN	Maltrieve Private, Virus Share [121]	[24]
CNN RNN	Unknown	[25]
CNN (Dynamic)	Unknown	[39]
DNN	Private data of Jotti commercial	[29]

DNN	Internal Microsoft dataset	[40]
DNN	DREBIN [107]	[45]
DNN	Microsoft corporation provided dataset	[44]
Autoencoders (Denoising)	C4 Security dataset	[43]
RNN	Internal Microsoft dataset	[23]
RNN	Virus Total [117], Alexa [60]	[36]
RBM	Contagio [118] Google Play Store [116]	[21]
RBM	Contagio [118], Google Play Store [116], Genome Project [120]	[22]
RBM	Comodo Cloud [119], Security Center	[26]
RBM	Virus share [121],Google play store [116]	[35]
RBM	Self-generated dataset	[34]
RBM	VirusTotal [117], DREBIN [107], Google Play [116], Genome Project [120]	[27]
RBM	Comodo Cloud [119], Security Center	[28]
RBM	Unknown	[38]
RBM	Unknown	[31]
Autoencoder	Challenge of Classification of Microsoft Malware[108],NSL-KDD [115]	[46]
DNN	Malware of traffic data, VirusShare, Kaspersky, MalShare, Malware sample	[37]

Table 1. DL methods for Malware Detection and Classification

Cyber Attack	DL Method	Dataset	Research Paper
Intrusion Detection	Autoencoder	KDDCUP 1999 [114]	[56]
	Autoencoder	KDDCUP 1999 [114]	[62]
	Autoencoder	KDDCUP 1999 [114]	[63]
	Autoencoder	NSL-KDD [115]	[61]
	Autoencoder	Network Experiments and Open-Car-Test-bed	[60]
	Autoencoder	NSL-KDD [115]	[70]
	Autoencoder	CIDDS-001 [127]	[54]
	Ladder Networks (Autoencoder)	KDD 1999 [114]	[71]
Autoencoder RBM	KDD 1999 [114]		[53]
Autoencoder	Custom		[55]
CNN	CTU-13 [124], IXIA [131]		[56]
	CNN (dilated) Autoencod	CTU-UNB [124, 125], Contagio-CTU-UNB [125]	[20]
DNN	KDDCUP 1999 [114]		[58]
DNN	simulator of Cooja network		[59]
DNN	NSL-KDD [115]		[69]
RBM	KDDCUP 1999 [114]		[49]

RNN	KDDCUP 1999 [114]	[67]
RNN	UNM, ADFA-LD, KDDCUP-1998 [114] data sets	[65]
RNN	KDDCUP-1999 and additional [114], unique data	[66]
RNN	Custom	[46]
RNN	KDD 1999 [114]	[68]
RNN	KDD 1999 [114]	[64]
RNN	NSL-KDD [115]	[57]
RBM	NSL-KDD [115]	[47]
RBM	KDD 1999 [114]	[50]
RBM	NSL-KDD [115]	[51]
RBM	NSL-KDD [115] KDDCUP 1999 [114] UNSW-NB15	[48]
RBM Autoencoder	KDD 1999[114]	[52]
RBM RNN	CTU-13[124]	[158]
Autoencoder	Challenge of Microsoft Classification of Malware [108], NSL-KDD [115]	[46]

Table 2. DL methods for Intrusion Detection

Cyber Attack	DL Method	Dataset	Research Paper
File Type Identification	Autoencoder	Internal Dataset	[81]
Identification of Network Traffic	Autoencoder	Honeypot dataset resulted internally	[83]
Spam Identification	Autoencoder	ISCX-VPN-nonVPN-traffic dataset[164]	[82]
	Autoencoder	EnronSpam [126], PU1, PU2, PU3, PU4	[84]
	RBM	EnronSpam [126] SpamAssassin [127] LingSpam [128]	[85]
Impersonation Attacks	Autoencoder	AWID[156]	[86]
User Authentication	Autoencoder	Custom	[87]
DGA	CNN	Alexa [104], Private Dataset	[88]
	GAN	Alexa [104]	[89]
	RNN	Alexa [104], OSINT [105]	[90]
	RNN	Alexa [104], DGArchive [106], OSINT [105]	[91]
	CNN RNN	Alexa [104], OSINT [105]	[92]
	CNN RNN	Alexa [104], DGArchive [106]	[93]
	RNN	Alexa [104], OSINT [105]	[94]
Attack of Drive-by Download	RNN	Malware Capture Facility Project Dataset	[95]
	CNN	KDD 1999 [114]	[119]
	CNN	honeypot setup, Malware Bytes, Malware domain list, Alexa [104]	[118]
Traffic Identification	CNN	ISCX VPN-nonVPN traffic dataset [164]	[163]
Insider Threat	DNN RNN	CERT Dataset v6.2 [123]	[166]
Anomaly Detection	RNN	Custom	[169]
Keystroke Verification	RNN	Custom	[170]
False Data Ejection	RBM	Custom	[172]

Table 3. DL methods for Other Frequent Cyber Attack

Dataset Name	Features	Reference
KDD Cup 99	Intrusion Detection, R2L, DoS, Probing	[114]
NSL-KDD	Network Intrusion Detection	[115]

CTU-13	Scenarios of thirteen captures of various samples in botnet are included in this dataset. Every scenario is taken in a file like pcap. That file consists of every packet of 3 kinds of traffic.	[59]	
Alexa [104] AWID	Alexa offers us access to a set of web sites. Alexa can be expected legitimate. Comprehensive		
Wi-Fi network benchmark dataset.	Detect impersonation attacks	[100]	DGA
38 classes with 168,900 samples		[106]	
CTU	Consists of different, real botnet attacks and labels.	[103]	
OSINT	OSINT DGA feeds from Bambenek Consulting. DGA (Domain Generation Algorithm) are used by malware	[105]	
VirusShare	A repository of 38,005,488 malware samples.	[121]	
DREBIN	1,20,000 android applications are contained in this dataset.	[107]	
Microsoft Malware Classification Challenge	Every malware has a unique value of 20-character hash recognizing the file and a unique Id, and a Class. An integer value is represented names of nine-family. This malware can belong.	[108]	
CERT Insider Threat Dataset v6.2	System logs spanning 516 days are included. This dataset contains over 130 million events. Approximately 400 of them are malicious.	[109, 110]	
EnronSpam	The total number of emails (legitimate and spam) is 5975. The ratio of spam to legitimate rate is 1:3.	[111]	
SpamAssassin	It can differentiate effectively between non-spam and spam in between cases of 95% to 100%, relying on the kind of mail taken and Bayesian filter with training.	[112]	
Malware Training Sets	Zeus:2014 samples, Crypto:2024 samples, Locker:434 samples, APT1:292 samples.	[123]	
CIDDS-001	The dataset consists a large number of traffic instances. 153026 instances are collected from External Server. 172839 instances are collected from OpenStack Server.	[127]	
Public malware API call sequence dataset ISCX	API call sequences (Malware): 42,797, API call sequences (goodware): 1,079. Each API call sequence: First 100 API calls that are consecutively non-repeated	[130]	
VPN-nonVPN traffic dataset	It has a category of 14-traffic: P2P, VOIP, VPN-P2P,VPN-VOIP, etc. Wireshark and tcpdump were used for capturing the traffic generated about 28GB of data.	[131]	

Table 4. Explanation of Cyber Security Datasets in DL

Figure 8: Several performance metrics

However, DL takes too Table 1 summarizes various DL methods applied by researchers for malware detection and classification. Most researchers use the restricted Boltzmann machine (RBM) method. Table 2 summarizes various DL methods applied for intrusion detection. Most researchers use autoencoder and RNN method. Table 3 summarizes the DL method used to detect other types of cyber-attacks. The other datasets used in various research papers for the classification of various threats have been described in Table 4 with short details. Several performance metrics are depicted in Figure 8.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF DL METHODS APPLIED IN VARIOUS RESEARCH PAPERS

Deep learning (DL) models have significantly outperformed traditional machine learning (ML) methods, as well as signature-based and rule-based techniques, in addressing cybersecurity challenges. Our review of 85 papers highlights a

strong focus on malware classification and network intrusion detection. Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBMs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are the most frequently utilized DL techniques, with RBMs being popular due to the scarcity of labeled data, which often leads to pre-training on unlabeled data. RNNs are effective for time series problems, making them suitable for various cybersecurity tasks. In contrast, network intrusion detection methods exhibited accuracy rates ranging from 44% to 100%. RBMs achieved 99.72% accuracy on custom datasets, while LSTMs reached 99.80% on the KDD Cup 99 dataset. The ability to detect intrusions heavily depends on the type and quantity of attacks, as well as the ratio of benign to malicious data, often leading to data generated through virus simulations and reverse engineering.

Methods	Data used	Paper	Precision	FNR	Accuracy	F1-Score	TPR
DBN	KDD CUP 99	[47]	92.33%		93.49%		
CNN and RNN (LSTM and Softmax layer)	Virus Share [121], Private	[24]	85.6%		89.4%		89.4%
RBM	Custom	[34]			99.72%		90.1%
LSTM	Alexa, DG Archive	[93]			98.96%		74.05%
RNN	UNM, ADFA-LD, KDDCUP 1998 [114] data sets	[65]	99.31%	4.62%	96%	97.31%	95.38%

Table 5. Performance Analysis of various DL methods

While deep learning (DL) offers advantages in various sectors, it also poses challenges in cybersecurity. Specialists may waste time on false positives, and automated systems can inadvertently block access to critical services or overlook cyber-attacks. Cybersecurity is vital for the Internet of Things (IoT), especially during pandemics like COVID-19. IoT can assist in controlling virus spread through temperature screening, contact tracing, and early detection of infections. However, the evolving nature of cyber-attacks complicates security for low-power IoT devices, highlighting the importance of effective cybersecurity measures.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the utilization of DL for the advancement of security in a system. As attacks of malice against cyber systems' networks are sophisticating, the cyber defender has to be sophisticated also. Cybersecurity staffs should be able to comment and utilize unique signatures to detect unique attacks. Approaches of DL in cybersecurity applications present smart chances toward the detection of unique malware variants and attacks of zero-day. In this review, we have described the applications of DL systems to different types of cybersecurity attack types. These attacks are mainly application software, targeted networks, data and host system. Likewise, this paper illustrates that the standard datasets are very important to advancing DL in the cybersecurity domain. The paper aims draw a complete review of DL methods, the needs of DL in cybersecurity, and to promote future research of DL in

cybersecurity. Finally, this article elaborates on the use case scenarios of IoT in the context of COVID-19, and showcases the importance of cybersecurity for IoT devices.

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